

BRYOMOLECULES

Report on phytochemical profile of 50 moss accessions

D2.1

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Information

Table 1 - Document information

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Acknowledgement and disclaimer

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The BRYOMOLECULES project

Liverworts, an ancient group of land plants, are a rich yet underexploited source of a wide range of biologically active compounds with high potential for the bioeconomy sector as ingredients of cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals. However, their slow growth rate in nature and the consequent difficulty in obtaining large amounts of single compounds have, until now, severely hindered the in-depth exploration and exploitation of the full spectrum of activities of liverwort secondary metabolites. Recent breakthroughs in the identification of some of the genes involved in the early steps of liverwort-specific compounds suggest that, in addition to the establishment of improved methods for growth in axenic conditions, reconstruction of liverwort metabolic pathways in heterologous systems is a promising way forth towards the practical exploitation of liverwort biochemical diversity and its industrial scale up.

BRYOMOLECULES will provide actionable knowledge on European bryophyte species and their biosynthetic genes, which can be used to produce sustainable, bio-based cosmetics and pharmaceuticals ingredients for the European market.

To do so, the BRYOMOLECULES project will use a combination of the cultivation of axenic cultures and the production of the active compounds in heterologous systems to define the most suitable production platform(s) for their large-scale production. The project will achieve a very sustainable use of the chemical diversity of wild EU bryophyte species, a largely untapped source of high-added-value natural products, without significant impacts on their biodiversity.

Besides the identification of relevant lead compounds for cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals, another major impact of the project will be the production and release according to FAIR principles of a database of metabolites and biosynthetic genes of European bryophyte species that will fuel in the years to come the development of novel bio-based products based on bryophyte-derived lead compounds, according to the concept of EU valorising biodiversity for EU bioeconomy.

Project Consortium Members

Table 3 - Consortium members

<p>FONDAZIONE EDMUND MACH dal 1874</p>	Fondazione Edmund Mach (FEM)
<p>HUB INNOVAZIONE TRENINO</p>	Fondazione HUB Innovazione Trentino (HIT) FEM LTP
<p>UNIVERSITÉ JEAN MONNET SAINT-ETIENNE</p>	Université Jean Monnet, Saint-Etienne (UJM)
<p>PAT Plant Advanced Technologies</p>	Plant Advanced Technologies PAT SA (PAT)
<p>Bionos Testing Efficiency</p>	Bionos Biotech SI (BIONOS)
<p>LUNDS UNIVERSITET</p>	Lunds Universitet (LU)
<p>UNIWERSYTET MEDYCZNY W LUBLINIE</p>	Uniwersytet Medyczny w Lublinie (UM)
<p>ESF</p>	European Science Foundation (ESF)

Summary

In this deliverable, the metabolomic profiles resulting from the around 50 accessions of mosses coming from axenic culture is reported and organized in a summary table that will serve in the metabolic gene identification (WP3; T3.2) and the project public database (WP3; T3.3). The report also includes conclusions on chemical diversity and chemotaxonomy of European mosses.

Introduction

Bryophytes are an underexplored source of bioactive metabolites. Within WP2, metabolomic datasets were generated to characterise their chemical diversity. This deliverable focuses on mosses and supports chemotaxonomy, identification of bioactive molecules, and integration with WP3–WP5.

This deliverable presents metabolomic profiling of 57 moss accessions, which correspond to 48 moss species cultivated under axenic conditions. The title originally referred to 50 accessions; however, the dataset was expanded to 57 and the report reflects this updated number consistently. Metabolites identified include flavonoids, phenolic acids, terpenoids, sterols, and fatty acids. The dataset supports bioprospecting, chemotaxonomy, and downstream WP3–WP5 activities.

Material and Methods

Sample material

57 moss accessions derived from axenic cultures were analysed.

Extraction procedures

Moss samples were extracted using diethyl ether followed by methanol/chloroform (2:1, v/v). In the first step, the material was homogenized in a mortar with diethyl ether. The extracts were transferred to vials, evaporated to dryness, and stored at -20°C until further analysis. After evaporation of diethyl ether at room temperature in the mortar, the remaining material was re-extracted with methanol/chloroform (2:1, v/v). The extracts were transferred to 20 mL glass vials and subjected to ultrasound treatment for 20 minutes. Subsequently, the samples were filtered through a 17 mm, $0.22\ \mu\text{m}$ PTFE hydrophobic syringe filter, transferred to vials, and evaporated to dryness. The dried extracts were stored at -20°C until further analysis.

Sequential extraction using diethyl ether and methanol/chloroform (2:1 v/v) was applied. Extracts were filtered, evaporated, and stored at -20°C prior to analysis.

Analytical platforms

GC–MS–EI–Q and HPLC–HRAM–MS–ESI–QToF were used for metabolomic profiling, including iterative MS/MS acquisition for improved annotation.

GC–MS–EI–Q analyses were carried out using a Shimadzu GC-2010 Plus GC instrument coupled to a Shimadzu QP2010 Ultra mass spectrometer with a single quadrupole mass analyzer and an electron impact ionisation source (Shimadzu Europa GmbH, Duisburg, Germany). Samples were injected to a fused silica capillary column ZB-5 MS (30 m, 0.25 mm i.d.) with a film thickness of 0.25 mm (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) in the split mode (1:5). Injection temperature was 250°C. Temperature program started at 50°C with 3 minutes of hold time then was increased up to 250°C with 5°C/min rate and 5 minutes of hold time, in the final step gradient ended at 325°C with 10°C/min rate and 4.5 minutes of hold time with 60 minutes of total program time. Helium was used as carrier gas and its flow was set at 1.0 mL/min. MS chromatograms were acquired in scan mode with 5 minutes of solvent cut time and with scan range 40-500 amu. Ion source temperature was set at 220°C and the ionization energy was 70 eV, which is consistent with the majority of GC-MS spectra libraries. A homologous series of n-alkanes (C8–C24) were analysed under the same operating conditions in order to determine the retention time indices.

HPLC–HRAM–MS–ESI–QToF analyses were performed on Agilent 1200 Infinity HPLC chromatograph coupled to Agilent 6530B QTOF system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) with electrospray ion source. The chromatographic separation was carried out on a Synergi Fusion RP column (2.5 µm i.d., 100 x 3 mm) supported by a suitable guard column (Phenomenex Inc, Torrance, CA, USA). The solvents system comprised of solvent A (water with 0.1% formic acid v/v) and solvent B (acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid v/v) was used in the following gradient: 20 - 60% B for 7 min, 60 - 100% B for 5 min, and 100% B for 18 min at the flow rate of 0.6 mL/min and with column temperature set at 40°C. Mass spectrometry data were collected using following parameters: nebulizer pressure of 40 psig, drying gas temp of 325°C and drying gas flow of 12 L/min, collision energies of 20 and 40 eV, sheath gas temp and flow were 325°C and 12 L/min, skimmer: 65V, capillary voltage: 4000V and fragmentor: 140V. Reference ions solution were injected into the ion source during all analysis. Total ion chromatograms were acquired in negative ionization mode using scan mode to obtain the most relevant data for metabolomic analysis. For compound identification, iterative samples were prepared and injected three times in the iterative mode using the autoMS acquisition mode. The iterative samples were prepared by mixing small aliquots from approximately 12 samples. All extracts were represented in the iterative samples.

Data processing and identification

Data were processed using MS-DIAL, including peak detection, deconvolution and alignment.

Processing included:

- QC filtering (RSD \leq 30%),
- blank subtraction (Sample/Blank \geq 3),
- signal drift correction (LOESS),
- normalisation (PQN, log transformation, Pareto scaling).

Metabolite identification followed MSI levels (1–4), using spectral libraries, standards and MS/MS fragmentation. Metabolites were identified using available spectral libraries, reference

standards, and characteristic fragmentation patterns. Annotation confidence followed MSI guidelines.

Quality control

QCheck samples were included in both GC–MS and LC–MS metabolomic analyses to assess and correct for MS signal stability throughout the analytical run. Separate QCheck samples were prepared for ether extracts and methanol–chloroform extracts by combining small aliquots of each extract. The QCheck samples were injected at the beginning and end of each worklist, as well as several times throughout the analytical sequence.

Quality assurance also included:

- monitoring signal stability,
- filtering low-reproducibility features.

Methodological limitations

During the analyses, we encountered several problems. First of all, we had to work with very small amounts of moss material. The second problem was related to the large variation in sample amounts, which made it impossible to prepare all samples simultaneously at the same reasonable concentration of plant material. Moreover, we also faced problems with the solubility of the obtained extracts, especially in polar solvents, which resulted in the need to use a higher percentage of mobile phase B (20%) at the beginning of the gradient program in the LC–MS analyses.

Limitations also include semi-quantitative data with some tentative identifications. It is primarily due to the limited and variable amounts of plant material available for metabolomic analysis, which constrained the application of absolute quantification approaches. As a result, relative signal intensities from GC–MS and LC–MS were used to compare metabolite profiles, but they do not reflect precise concentrations. In addition, a subset of metabolites was assigned as tentative identifications, based on accurate mass and fragmentation data without confirmation using reference standards, which may include structurally related compounds or isomers. Despite these limitations, the dataset remains robust and suitable for comparative metabolomics and chemotaxonomic analyses.

Results and Discussion

Metabolite diversity

The metabolomic analysis of 57 moss accessions revealed a broad diversity of secondary and primary metabolites, spanning multiple chemical classes with distinct biosynthetic origins. The major groups detected included:

- **Flavonoids** (e.g., kaempferol, apigenin, luteolin and their glycosides)

- **Phenolic acids** (e.g., caffeic, chlorogenic, p-coumaric acids)
- **Coumarins** (e.g., esculin, esculetin, fraxin)
- **Terpenoids** (including sesquiterpenes and diterpenoids such as eremophilane and abietane derivatives)
- **Sterols and tocopherols** (e.g., β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, γ -tocopherol)
- **Fatty acids and derivatives**, including polyunsaturated fatty acids and oxidised C18 compounds

LC–MS significantly extended chemical coverage, whereas GC–MS datasets showed reduced feature numbers after QC filtering, reflecting analytical constraints.

Figure 1. PCA score plot after LC-MS analysis of all samples (including QC and blanks) showing overall metabolomic variation.

A conserved core metabolome was identified across mosses, including organic acids, phytol and sterols, and oxidised fatty acids. In contrast, several metabolite classes exhibited taxon-specific distribution, including:

- flavonoid glycosides and rare C-glycosides
- biflavonoids (e.g., volkensiflavone)
- coumarins (notably enriched in Polytrichaceae)
- selected diterpenoids and phenolic derivatives

These compounds contribute to chemical individuality and are responsible for the separation of taxa at genus and family level (figure 2).

Figure 2. PCA biplot indicating metabolites present in the ether extracts contributing to sample separation (loadings).

Metabolites as indicated by loadings in PCA-biplot (figure 2) were identified on Level 1 (Confirmed/Identified Metabolites) and 2 (Putatively Annotated Compounds). Table 1 containing the first 8 compounds.

Table 1. The first 8 metabolites contributing to PCA separation

No	MS-DIAL AID	Rt [min]	Precursor m/z	Formula	Adduct	Library hit	Library	MSI Level
1.	AID_309	2.79	121.0293	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂	[M-H]-	Benzoic acid	(A)	2
2.	AID_987	4.17	187.0969	C ₉ H ₁₆ O ₄	[M-H]-	Azelaic acid	(A)	2
3.	AID_1591	7.83	241.0868	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃	[M-H]-	4-methoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene-2,7-diol	(A)	2
4.	AID_1897	3.63	261.1345	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ O ₆	[M-H]-	9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid	(A)	2
5.	AID_1989	6.22	269.0458	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	[M-H]-	Apigenin	(B)	2
6.	AID_2423	10.42	295.2278	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₃	[M-H]-	9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid	(A)	2
7.	AID_2457	6.46	299.0552	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	[M-H]-	Diosmetin	(B)	2
8.	AID_3109	6.21	329.2315	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₅	[M-H]-	(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid	(A)	2

The metabolomic data demonstrate that moss secondary metabolites provide robust chemotaxonomic markers, particularly:

- **Flavonoids and their derivatives**, which show high structural diversity and taxon-dependent distribution
- **Phenolic acids**, which are ubiquitous but vary in composition and abundance
- **Coumarins**, which display strong diagnostic value for specific families (e.g., Polytrichaceae)
- Certain taxa were characterised by enriched or distinctive metabolite profiles, for example:
 - species with high levels of **flavonoid glycosides**
 - taxa accumulating **biflavonoids or rare phenolics**
 - coumarin-rich species with clear family-level specificity

Overall, the data support the use of metabolomic fingerprints as a **complementary tool to morphological and genetic classification**, particularly at **genus and family levels**, where clear chemical differentiation was observed (figure 3).

Figure 3. Hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) showing grouping of samples based on chemical similarity.

These results confirm the usefulness of metabolomics in taxonomic classification.

Bioprospecting relevance

The metabolomic profiles generated in this study provide a direct basis for bioprospecting and lead selection, by:

- identifying species with high chemical richness,
- highlighting taxa producing rare or structurally diverse metabolites,
- detecting compounds belonging to classes known for bioactivity (e.g., flavonoids, terpenoids, coumarins).

Particularly relevant features include:

- occurrence of biflavonoids and phenolic derivatives associated with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity
- presence of terpenoids and sterols with potential pharmacological or cosmetic applications
- species-specific metabolites that may represent novel lead compounds

These findings enable the prioritisation of candidate species for biological assays (WP5) and support the selection of target compounds for further development and production.

Contribution to WP3-WP5

The D2.1 dataset constitutes a key input for downstream work packages:

WP3 – Biosynthetic pathway elucidation

- metabolite profiles provide phenotypic outputs for correlation with genomic and transcriptomic data
- enable identification of candidate pathways for secondary metabolite biosynthesis

WP4 – Heterologous production

- identification of target compounds supports selection of pathways for reconstruction in microbial or plant hosts
- knowledge of metabolite diversity guides prioritisation of industrially relevant molecules

WP5 – Exploitation and applications

- data enable selection of lead species and compounds for biological testing
- support development of cosmeceutical and pharmaceutical applications

Importantly, the use of harmonised extraction, analytical methods, and sample coding ensures that the dataset is fully interoperable across work packages, facilitating integration into the BRYOMOLECULES database and supporting FAIR data principles

Conclusions

The metabolomic profiling of 57 moss accessions demonstrates:

- a conserved metabolic core across taxa,
- significant chemotaxonomic differentiation,
- strong potential for bioprospecting and application.

The dataset provides a robust foundation for downstream WP3–WP5 activities and supports the overall objectives of the BRYOMOLECULES project.

Annex 1

Metabolites were grouped into major chemical classes, including fatty acids and their derivatives, terpenoids, sterols, phenolic compounds, volatile organic compounds, and aliphatic hydrocarbons. This classification enabled interpretation of metabolomic profiles in a chemotaxonomic context.

Metabolites identified only in a given sample are marked in **green** and **red**.

No	Species	Sample code	Group of metabolites	Identified compounds
1.	<i>Pleurozium schreberi</i>	X124_SW_MC_7 X124_SW_Et_7 V25_SW_MC_7 V25_SW_Et_7	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid Sucrose Sorbitol
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Kaempferol-3-O-deoxyhexosyl-hexoside-7-O-deoxyhexosyl-hexoside Myrtucommulone B
			Fatty acids and their esters	17-Octadecynoic acid 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid Azelaic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester Palmitoleic acid Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester

Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-Methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Docosene 1-Hexacosanol 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane, 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl- Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Hexadecane, 7-methyl- n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Octacosyl acetate Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl-
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Globulol Patchulane Nootkatene trans-Geranylgeraniol Phytol Forbol

			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p> <p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene</p>
			<p>Other compounds</p> <p>Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4-dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl- d-Docecalactone g-Tocopherol Vitamin E L-Asparagine 3-Methyladipic acid 9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid Undecanedioic acid 2-Phenylpropenal Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-</p>
2.	<i>Grimmia pulvinata</i>	<p>XI24_SW_MC_10 XI24_SW_Et_10 V25_SW_MC_10 V25_SW_Et_10</p>	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p> <p>Malic acid Sucrose Sorbitol</p> <p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p> <p>Apigenin 6,8-digalactoside Chlorogenic acid 4-O-Caffeoylquinic acid Rutin Isorhamnetin 3-O-glucoside Myrtucommulone B Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl</p> <p>Fatty acids and their esters</p> <p>Azelaic acid 9-Hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA</p>

	<p>DHA methyl ester EPA methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid ethyl ester (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid Undecanedioic acid Sebacic acid 9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone 4-Hexen-3-one 2-Phenylpropenal</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate Pentatriacontane Tetraatriacontane Eicosane, 10-methyl Heptadecane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Globulol Patchulane trans-Geranylgeraniol Phytol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-b-ionone Gelomulide N (diterpenoid)</p>

				<p>9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid</p> <p>Forbol</p> <p>Citronellyl formate</p> <p>Nootkatene</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol</p> <p>Stigmasterol</p> <p>Stigmasteryl acetate</p> <p>Campesterol</p> <p>Brassicasterol</p> <p>Cycloartenyl acetate</p> <p>b-Amyrin</p> <p>Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol</p> <p>Vitamin E</p> <p>d-Docecalactone</p> <p>Cyclodecanol</p> <p>Cyclohexane derivatives</p>
3.	<i>Hedwigia ciliata</i>	XI24_SW_MC_11 XI24_SW_Et_11	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Adenine</p> <p>Malic acid</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Kaempferol-3-O-deoxyhexosyl-hexoside-7-O-deoxyhexosyl-hexoside</p> <p>Apigenin 6,8-digalactoside</p> <p>Caffeic acid</p> <p>Apigenin-7-O-dihexoside</p> <p>Isovanillic acid (tentative)</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid</p> <p>17-Octadecynoic acid</p> <p>cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid</p> <p>cis-13-Eicosenoic acid</p> <p>Palmitoleic acid</p> <p>gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA)</p> <p>DHA</p> <p>DHA, methyl ester</p> <p>EPA, methyl ester</p> <p>6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p> <p>(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid</p> <p>(10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid</p> <p>5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester</p>

	<p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z), methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester</p> <p>9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl-</p> <p>1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl-</p> <p>2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl-</p> <p>2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p> <p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 3-methyl-</p> <p>Hexadecane, 7-methyl-</p> <p>Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Tridecane, 5-propyl-</p> <p>Undecane, 2-methyl-</p> <p>Cyclohexadecane</p> <p>Cyclohexane, tetradecyl-</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene</p> <p>a-Thujene</p> <p>d-Thujone</p> <p>Myrtenol</p> <p>Lavandulyl acetate</p> <p>Citronellyl formate</p> <p>9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid</p> <p>g-Costol</p>

				<p>Globulol Patchulane Gelomulide N Forbol trans-Geranylgeraniol Phytol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15- Tetramethylhexadeca-... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2- hexadecen-1-ol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4- dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
4.	<i>Hypnum cupressiforme</i>	XI24_SW_MC_12 XI24_SW_Et_12	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Caffeic acid 2-acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Myrtucommulone B Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester</p>

	<p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid ethyl ester</p> <p>cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid</p> <p>cis-13-Eicosenoic acid</p> <p>gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA)</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid methyl esters</p> <p>Palmitoleic acid</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one</p> <p>2-Undecanone</p> <p>d-Docecalactone</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane derivatives</p> <p>Heptane derivatives</p> <p>Hexadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane derivatives</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Triacontyl acetate</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>4-Methyltricosane</p> <p>Undecane derivatives</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene</p> <p>a-Thujene</p> <p>d-Thujone</p> <p>Myrtenol</p> <p>Globulol</p> <p>Patchulane</p> <p>(9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid)</p> <p>Abietic acid</p> <p>Forbol</p> <p>Phytol</p>

				trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β -Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy- β -ionone 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl derivatives
			Sterols and triterpenoids	β -Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β -Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	γ -Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative
5.	<i>Rhynchostegium riparioides</i>	XI24_SW_MC_18 XI24_SW_Et_18	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Caffeic acid Volkensiflawon (biflavonoid)
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid (<i>oxylipin</i>) 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester

	Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane, 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl- Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Globulol Patchulane Gelomulide N trans-Geranylgeraniol Phytol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol g-Costol (sesquiterpenoid) Forbol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4-dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
6.	<i>Eurhynchium striatum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_20 XI24_SW_Et_20	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Caffeic acid p-Coumaric acid Volkensiflawon (biflavonoid) Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (<i>oxylipin</i>) (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid (<i>oxylipin</i>) 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane, 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl- Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Globulol Patchulane</p>

				<p>Abietic acid Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15- Tetramethylhexadeca-... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2- hexadecen-1-ol Forbol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4- dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
7.	<i>Racomitrium macounii</i>	XI24_SW_MC_28 XI24_SW_Et_28	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) Kaempferol Luteolin Apigenin Volkensiflawon (biflavonoid)</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13- trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15- dienoic acid (<i>oxylipin</i>) (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9- enoic acid (<i>oxylipin</i>) 9-hydroxy-10,12- octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester</p>

	<p>6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl-</p> <p>1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl-</p> <p>2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl-</p> <p>2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p> <p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>4-Methyltricosane</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 3-methyl-</p> <p>Hexadecane, 7-methyl-</p> <p>Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Tridecane, 5-propyl-</p> <p>Undecane, 2-methyl-</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>Triacontyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetale Citronellyl formate 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid Globulol Patchulane Abietic acid Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol Forbol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4-dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
8.	<i>Schistidium papillosum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_30 XI24_SW_Et_30	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	-
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Eriodictyol Kaempferol Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester

	<p>5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl-</p> <p>1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl-</p> <p>2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl-</p> <p>2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>4-Methyltricosane</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 3-methyl-</p> <p>Hexadecane, 7-methyl-</p> <p>Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Tridecane, 5-propyl-</p> <p>Undecane, 2-methyl-</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>Triacontyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Globulol Patchulane Gelomulide N Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol Forbol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4-dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
9.	<i>Dicranoweissia cirrata</i>	<p>XI24_SW_MC_41 XI24_SW_Et_41 V25_SW_MC_41 V25_SW_Et_41</p>	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Malic acid Sucrose Sorbitol</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Luteolin Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester</p>

	<p>EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid hexadecyl ester Azelaic acid 9-Hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 3-Methyladipic acid</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone 4-Hexen-3-one 1,6-Heptadiene 2,6-Octadiene 2-Hexene</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyltricosane Eicosane, 10-methyl Heptadecane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetratriacontane Tridecane Undecane Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone derivatives (E,E,E)-tetramethylhexadeca derivatives 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Gelomulide N g-Costol Forbol Nootkatene
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivatives
10.	<i>Dicranella heteromalla</i>	XI24_SW_MC_42 XI24_SW_Et_42 V25_SW_MC_42 V25_SW_Et_42	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid Sucrose Sorbitol
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy
			Fatty acids and their esters	(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester

	<p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid ethyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid (oba izomery estrowe)</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid hexadecyl ester</p> <p>Azelaic acid</p> <p>9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid</p> <p>9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid</p> <p>Undecanedioic acid</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Undecanone</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one</p> <p>1,6-Heptadiene</p> <p>2,6-Octadiene</p> <p>2-Hexene</p> <p>2-Phenylpropenal</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p> <p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>4-Methyltricosane</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl</p> <p>Heptadecane derivatives</p> <p>Hexadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Tridecane</p> <p>Undecane</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>Triacontyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone derivatives (E,E,E)-tetramethylhexadeca derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Gelomulide N Forbol Nootkatene
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivatives
11.	<i>Pseudoscleropodium purum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_43 XI24_SW_Et_43	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Volkensiflawon (<i>biflavonoid</i>)
			Fatty acids and their esters	9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl-</p> <p>1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl-</p> <p>2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl-</p> <p>2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>4-Methyldocosane</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane, 3-methyl-</p> <p>Hexadecane, 7-methyl-</p> <p>Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Tridecane, 5-propyl-</p> <p>Undecane, 2-methyl-</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene</p> <p>a-Thujene</p> <p>d-Thujone</p> <p>Myrtenol</p> <p>Lavandulyl acetate</p> <p>Citronellyl formate</p> <p>9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid</p>

				<p>Globulol Patchulane Gelomulide N Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15- Tetramethylhexadeca-... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2- hexadecen-1-ol Forbol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4- dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
12.	<i>Atrichum undulatum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_46 XI24_SW_Et_46	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Luteolin Caffeic acid p-Coumaric acid Gentisic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy Coumarins: Esculin Fraxin monohydrate Esculetin Hydroxy-fraxin</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA</p>

	<p>DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone 4-Hexen-3-one 1,6-Heptadiene 2,6-Octadiene 2-Hexene</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetradecane Tetratriacontane Tridecane Undecane Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate</p>

				<p>9.11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Globulol Patchulane Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone (E,E,E)-tetramethylhexadeca derivative 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol Forbol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene, 1-ethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-ethenyl-1,4-dimethyl- Cyclohexene, 4-propyl- Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
13.	<i>Bryum argenteum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_49 XI24_SW_Et_49	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Kaempferol Kaempferol hexoside Kaempferol dihexoside (isomers 1, 2) Kaempferol-3-O-malonyl-hexoside Luteolin Luteolin 7-O-glucoside Apigenin Apigenin-7-O-hexoside Apigenin-7-O-dihexoside Apigenin-7-glucoside Rutin Diosmetin-3-O-hexoside Isorhamnetin 3-O-neohesperidoside p-Hydroxybenzoic acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)-</p>

	Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl
Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone 4-Hexen-3-one 1,6-Heptadiene 2,6-Octadiene 2-Hexene 2-Phenylpropenal</p>

Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (różne izomery) Hexadecane (pochodne) Pentadecane (pochodne) Pentatriacontane Tetradecane Tetratriacontane Tridecane Undecane Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid Globulol Patchulane Gelomulide N Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone (E,E,E)-tetramethylhexadeca derivative 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol Forbol</p>
Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl-</p>

14.	<i>Cirriphyllum piliferum</i>	<p>XI24_SW_MC_52 XI24_SW_Et_52 V25_SW_MC_52 V25_SW_Et_52</p>	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Adenine Malic acid N-alpha-Acetyl-L-ornithine Sucrose Sorbitol</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Volkensiflawon (biflavonoid) Caffeic acid 4-Hydroxybenzoate Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (sample 1) DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone 4-Hexen-3-one 1,6-Heptadiene</p>			

	2,6-Octadiene 2-Hexene 2-Phenylpropenal
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Tridecane Undecane Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane Nootkatene Forbol Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol
Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane

				Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivatives
15.	<i>Bryoerythrophyllum recurvirostre</i>	XI24_SW_MC_60 XI24_SW_Et_60	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Volkensiflawon (biflavonoids) Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
			Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-

	2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane g-Costol 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Loliolide</p>

			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p> <p>Other compounds</p>	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p> <p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
16.	<i>Tortula aucionalon</i>	XI24_SW_MC_61 XI24_SW_Et_61	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p> <p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p> <p>Fatty acids and their esters</p>	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p> <p>Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy Coumarins: Esculin Esculetin</p> <p>Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters</p>

	<p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol</p>

				<p>Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Loliolide</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
17.	<i>Didymodon fallax</i>	XI24_SW_MC_78 XI24_SW_Et_78	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Esculin Volkensiflawon (biflavonoids) 2-acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)-</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p>

	<p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
18.	<i>Fissidens taxifolius</i>	XI24_SW_MC_80 XI24_SW_Et_80	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	-
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Gelomulide N</p>

				<p>Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
19.	<i>Orthotrichum cupulatum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_89 XI24_SW_Et_89	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	-
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Caffeic acid Volkensiflawon (biflavonoids) 2-acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid 2-Phenylpropenal</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid Gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester</p>

	Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone

				Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
20.	<i>Amblystegium cf. varium</i>	XI24_SW_MC_95 XI24_SW_Et_95	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Caffeic acid Volkensiflawon (biflavonoids) Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol

Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Gelomulide N (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol

				trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
21.	<i>Sphagnum medium</i>	XI24_SW_MC_97 XI24_SW_Et_97	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Chlorogenic acid 4-O-Caffeoylquinic acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)-
			Fatty acids and their esters	9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane g-Costol 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
22.	<i>Ephemerum serratum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_98 XI24_SW_Et_98	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	-
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	-
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, 15-methyl-, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester

	9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol

				trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
23.	<i>Aulacomnium andogynum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_101 XI24_SW_Et_101	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
			Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal

	<p>2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>

			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
24.	<i>Pohila bulbifera</i>	XI24_SW_MC_102 XI24_SW_Et_102	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Eriodictyol Kaempferol Luteolin p-Hydroxybenzoic acid p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) 2-acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester

	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol

				<p>b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
25.	<i>Diphyscium foliosum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_105 XI24_SW_Et_105	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>

Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol

			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
26.	<i>Polytrichum formosum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_107 XI24_SW_Et_107	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Esculin Esculetin Daphnetin Fraxetin Fraxin monohydrate 5,8-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-7- [(2S,3R,4S,5S,6R)-3,4,5- trihydroxy-6- (hydroxymethyl)oxan-2- yl]oxochromen-2-one (hydroxy- fraxin) Gentisic acid p-Coumaric acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2- propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1- dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12- octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
27.	<i>Dicranum majus</i>	XI24_SW_MC_120 XI24_SW_Et_120 XI24_SW_MC_145 XI24_SW_Et_145	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Luteolin Diosmetin-3-O-dideoxyhexosyl-hexoside Flavovilloside Volkensiflawon p-Hydroxybenzoic acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) 2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid (sample 1) 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA

	<p>DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)- 2-Phenylpropenal</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyltricosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid g-Costol Forbol Gelomulide N (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
28.	<i>Thuidium delicatulum</i>	X124_SW_MC_123 X124_SW_Et_123	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Luteolin Caffeic acid 2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA

	<p>DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
29.	<i>Isothecium alopecuroides</i>	XI24_SW_MC_124 XI24_SW_Et_124	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Caffeic acid 2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)-</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA</p>

	<p>DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
30.	<i>Barbula unguiculata</i>	XI24_SW_MC_128 XI24_SW_Et_128	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Luteolin Caffeic acid</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester</p>

	<p>5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl-</p> <p>1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl-</p> <p>2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl-</p> <p>2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>Hydrocarbons:</p> <p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>4-Methyldocosane</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-)</p> <p>Heptadecane, 3-methyl-</p> <p>Hexadecane, 7-methyl-</p> <p>Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Tridecane, 5-propyl-</p> <p>Undecane, 2-methyl-</p> <p>Esters:</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>Triacetyl acetate</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
31.	<i>Leptodictyum riparium</i>	XI24_SW_MC_131 XI24_SW_Et_131	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Eriodictyol Volkensiflawon Caffeic acid p-Coumaric acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl</p>

Fatty acids and their esters	(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecanal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-

				<p>Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
			<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, , and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15- Tetramethylhexadeca- 1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2- hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p>	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			<p>Other compounds</p>	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
32.	<i>Ditrichium pusillum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_132 XI24_SW_Et_132	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p>	<p>Malic acid</p>
			<p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p>	<p>Isovanillic acid (tentative) Eriodictyol Kaempferol Luteolin Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2- propenyl)-</p>

Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester) cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester Palmitoleic acid Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 4-Hexen-3-one 2-Undecanone d-Docecalactone</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Heptane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate 4-Methyldocosane Undecane derivative 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>

			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 2,6-Octadiene derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative
33.	<i>Plogiothecium undulatum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_136 XI24_SW_Et_136	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)-
			Fatty acids and their esters	9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester

	<p>5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester)</p> <p>cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid</p> <p>cis-13-Eicosenoic acid</p> <p>gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA)</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid (methyl esters)</p> <p>Palmitoleic acid</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Phenylpropenal</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one</p> <p>2-Undecanone</p> <p>d-Docecalactone</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane derivatives</p> <p>Heptane derivatives</p> <p>Hexadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane derivatives</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Triacetyl acetate</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>4-Methyltricosane</p> <p>Undecane derivative</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene</p> <p>a-Thujene</p> <p>d-Thujone</p> <p>Myrtenol</p> <p>Globulol</p> <p>Patchulane</p>

				<p>9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Abietic acid Forbol Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 2,6-Octadiene derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative</p>
34.	<i>Pogonatum aloides</i>	<p>XI24_SW_MC_140 XI24_SW_Et_140 V25_SW_MC_140 V25_SW_Et_140</p>	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p> <p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p>	<p>Malic acid Sucrose Sorbitol</p> <p>4-Hydroxybenzoate 2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy Coumarins: Esculin Fraxin monohydrate</p>
			Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid</p>

	<p>Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA Undecanedioic acid DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)- 2-Phenylpropenal</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl-</p>

				<p>Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
			<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid <i>Nootkatene (sample 2)</i> <i>Forbol (sample 1)</i> (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p>	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			<p>Other compounds</p>	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
35.	<i>Brachythecium rutabulum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_142 XI24_SW_Et_142	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p>	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p>
			<p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p>	<p>Eriodictyol Luteolin Volkensiflawon p-Hydroxybenzoic acid Caffeic acid p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) 2-acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Coumarins: Esculin</p>

	Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
	Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
	Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyltricosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane</p>

				<p>Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
			<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15- Tetramethylhexadeca- 1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2- hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p>	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			<p>Other compounds</p>	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
36.	<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	XI24_SW_MC_169 XI24_SW_Et_169	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p>	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p>
			<p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p>	<p>Eriodictyol Kaempferol Luteolin Apigenin-7-O-hexoside Apigenin-7-glucoside Luteolin 7-O-glucoside Cynaroside (luteolin glycoside) Rutin Kaempferol hexoside</p>

	<p>Kaempferol dihexoside (isomer 1) Kaempferol dihexoside (isomer 2) Kaempferol-3-O-malonyl-hexoside Quercetin hexoside (isomer 1) Quercetin-3-O-malonyl-hexoside Diosmetin-3-O-hexoside Isoschaftoside Apigenin 6,8-digalactoside Isovanillic acid (tentative) Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy</p>
Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-</p>

	<p>4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl-1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl-2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl-2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-2-Phenylpropenal</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl-Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>

			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p> <p>Other compounds</p>	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p> <p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
37.	<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	XI24_SW_MC_173 XI24_SW_Et_173	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p> <p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p> <p>Fatty acids and their esters</p>	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p> <p>p-Hydroxybenzoic acid Esculetin p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) Kaempferol Luteolin Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-</p> <p>9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester) cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid</p>

	<p>cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) Hexadecanoic acid (methyl esters) Palmitoleic acid Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Phenylpropenal 4-Hexen-3-one 2-Undecanone d-Docecalactone</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Heptane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate 4-Methyldocosane Undecane derivative 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Abietic acid Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 2,6-Octadiene derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative
38.	<i>Bartramia ithyphylla</i>	XI24_SW_MC_178 XI24_SW_Et_178 V25_SW_MC_178 V25_SW_Et_178	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid Sucrose Sorbitol
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Volkensiflavon (biflavonoid) Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-
			Fatty acids and their esters	9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester) cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) Palmitoleic acid Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester Undecanedioic acid

	<p>9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Phenylpropenal 4-Hexen-3-one 2-Undecanone d-Docecalactone</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Heptane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate 4-Methyltricosane Undecane derivative 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Gelomulide N (diterpenoid) Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone Nootkatene</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative
39.	<i>Homalia trichomanoides</i>	X124_SW_MC_188 X124_SW_Et_188	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Volkensiflavon (biflavonoid) 2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester)

	<p>cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) Hexadecanoic acid (methyl esters) Palmitoleic acid Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Phenylpropenal 4-Hexen-3-one 2-Undecanone d-Docecalactone</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Heptane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate 4-Methyldocosane Undecane derivative 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Abietic acid Forbol Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 2,6-Octadiene derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative
40.	<i>Anomodon viticulosus</i>	XI24_SW_MC_189 XI24_SW_Et_189	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	p-Coumaric acid Luteolin Volkensiflavon (biflavonoid) Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester) cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) Hexadecanoic acid (methyl esters) Palmitoleic acid Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Phenylpropenal 4-Hexen-3-one 2-Undecanone d-Docecalactone</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Heptane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate 4-Methyltricosane Undecane derivative 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 2,6-Octadiene derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative
41.	<i>Campylophyllum sommerfeltii</i>	XI24_SW_MC_204 XI24_SW_Et_204	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Caffeic acid Benzoic acid p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) (cis/trans)-Resveratrol 1 (cis/trans)-Resveratrol 2 Eriodictyol Kaempferol Luteolin 2-Acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester)</p> <p>cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid</p> <p>cis-13-Eicosenoic acid</p> <p>gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA)</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid (methyl esters)</p> <p>Palmitoleic acid</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one</p> <p>2-Undecanone</p> <p>d-Docecalactone</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-</p> <p>Heptadecane derivatives</p> <p>Heptane derivatives</p> <p>Hexadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentadecane derivatives</p> <p>Pentatriacontane</p> <p>Tetradecane derivatives</p> <p>Tetratriacontane</p> <p>Triacontyl acetate</p> <p>Hexacosyl acetate</p> <p>Octacosyl acetate</p> <p>4-Methyltricosane</p> <p>Undecane derivative</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene</p> <p>a-Thujene</p> <p>d-Thujone</p> <p>Myrtenol</p> <p>Globulol</p> <p>Patchulane</p> <p>9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid</p> <p>Abietic acid</p> <p>Forbol</p> <p>Phytol</p> <p>trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>

				<p>Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15- Tetramethylhexadeca... 2,6-Octadiene derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2- hexadecen-1-ol</p>
			Sterols and triterpenoids	<p>β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene</p>
			Other compounds	<p>γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative 4-methoxy-9,10- dihydrophenanthrene-2,7-diol</p>
42.	<i>Philonotis fontana</i>	XI24_SW_MC_213 XI24_SW_Et_213	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	<p>Adenine Malic acid</p>
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>Eriodictyol Kaempferol Luteolin Apigenin Chlorogenic acid p-Hydroxybenzoic acid Benzoic acid p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) 1-(3-ethyl-2,4-dihydroxy-6- methoxyphenyl)butan-1-one 2-acetoxy-4-pentadecylbenzoic acid Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2- propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1- dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1- dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy Coumarins: Esculin Esculetin</p>

Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl-</p>

				<p>Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl-Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl-Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl-Undecane, 2-methyl-Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
			<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>
			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p>	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene Hederagenin</p>
			<p>Other compounds</p>	<p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl-Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
43.	<i>Syntrichia ruraliformis</i>	<p>XI24_SW_MC_216 XI24_SW_Et_216 V25_SW_MC_216 V25_SW_Et_216</p>	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p>	<p>Adenine Malic acid Sucrose</p>
			<p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p>	<p>Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-</p>

	Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy-
Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid</p> <p>9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid</p> <p>(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid</p> <p>17-Octadecynoic acid</p> <p>DHA</p> <p>DHA, methyl ester</p> <p>EPA, methyl ester</p> <p>5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester</p> <p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester)</p> <p>cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid</p> <p>cis-13-Eicosenoic acid</p> <p>gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA)</p> <p>Hexadecanoic acid (methyl esters)</p> <p>Palmitoleic acid</p> <p>Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p> <p>9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal</p> <p>13-Tetradecenal</p> <p>2,4-Dodecadienal</p> <p>2,4-Undecadienal</p> <p>7-Hexadecenal</p> <p>Heptanal</p> <p>Nonanal</p> <p>Octadecanal</p> <p>2-Phenylpropenal</p> <p>4-Hexen-3-one</p> <p>2-Undecanone</p> <p>d-Docecalactone</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>1-Docosene</p> <p>1-Octadecene</p> <p>1-Hexacosanol</p> <p>n-Heptadecanol-1</p> <p>n-Tetracosanol-1</p> <p>Octacosanol</p> <p>Eicosane, 10-methyl-Heptadecane derivatives</p> <p>Heptane derivatives</p> <p>Hexadecane derivatives</p>

				Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate 4-Methyldocosane Undecane derivative 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Abietic acid Forbol Nootkatene Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-β-ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 2,6-Octadiene derivatives 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	β-Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
44.	<i>Pohlia nutans</i>	XI24_SW_MC_231 XI24_SW_Et_231	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Malic acid

Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	<p>p-Hydroxybenzoic acid Esculetin p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) Eriodictyol Kaempferol Luteolin Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl-</p>
Fatty acids and their esters	<p>Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (methyl + ethyl ester) cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) Hexadecanoic acid (methyl esters) Palmitoleic acid Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester</p>
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Phenylpropenal 4-Hexen-3-one 2-Undecanone d-Docecalactone</p>

	Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane derivatives Heptane derivatives Hexadecane derivatives Pentadecane derivatives Pentatriacontane Tetradecane derivatives Tetratriacontane Triacontyl acetate Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate 4-Methyl-docosane Undecane derivative 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
	Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Abietic acid Forbol Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate β -Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy- β -ionone (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca... 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol
	Sterols and triterpenoids	β -Sitosterol Campesterol Brassicasterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Cycloartenyl acetate β -Amyrin Squalene
	Other compounds	γ -Tocopherol Vitamin E Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane derivative

45.	<i>Pohlia drummondii</i>	X124_SW_MC_234 X124_SW_Et_234	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Luteolin p-Hydroxybenzoic acid p-Coumaric acid Isovanillic acid (tentative) Esculetin Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid (10E,15Z)-9,12,13-trihydroxyoctadeca-10,15-dienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol
Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl-			

	<p>4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl-1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl-2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl-2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl-2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-2-Phenylpropenal</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl-Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol Abietic acid (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol</p>

			<p>Sterols and triterpenoids</p> <p>Other compounds</p>	<p>b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene</p> <p>g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-</p>
46.	<i>Kiaeria blyttii</i>	XI24_SW_MC_246 XI24_SW_Et_246	<p>Nucleotides and primary metabolites</p> <p>Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds</p> <p>Fatty acids and their esters</p>	<p>Malic acid</p> <p>Phenol, 2-methoxy-6-(2-propenyl)- Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl Benzoic acid, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxy</p> <p>Azelaic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>

Volatile organic compounds (VOC)	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)- 2-Phenylpropenal</p>
Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyl-docosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacetyl acetate</p>
Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Forbol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol</p>

				trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
47.	<i>Ulota crispa</i>	V25_SW_MC_122 V25_SW_Et_122	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Adenine Malic acid Sucrose Sorbitol
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	4-Hydroxybenzoate Phenol, 4,6-di(1,1-dimethylethyl)-2-methyl
			Fatty acids and their esters	Azelaic acid 9-(2,3-dihydroxypropoxy)-9-oxononanoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid gamma-Linolenic acid (GLA) DHA DHA, methyl ester EPA, methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid, methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid, methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester

	<p>9,12-Octadecadienoic acid, ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid, methyl esters Tetradecanoic acid, hexadecyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol</p>
<p>Volatile organic compounds (VOC)</p>	<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 7-Hexadecenal Heptanal Nonanal Octadecanal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- 4-Hexen-3-one, 5-methyl- 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 2,4-Dodecadiene, (E,Z)-</p>
<p>Other aliphatic hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and their derivatives</p>	<p>14-methyl-(Z)-8-hexadecen-1-ol 1-Hexacosanol n-Heptadecanol-1 n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene 4-Methyldocosane Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane (2,6,10,15-tetramethyl-) Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- Pentadecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl- Pentatriacontane Tetradecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl- Tetratriacontane Tridecane, 5-propyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Hexacosyl acetate Octacosyl acetate Triacontyl acetate</p>
<p>Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)</p>	<p>a-Pinene a-Thujene d-Thujone Myrtenol Lavandulyl acetate Citronellyl formate Globulol Patchulane 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Nootkatene</p>

				(E,E,E)-3,7,11,15-Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol b-Ionone epoxide 3-Hydroxy-5,6-epoxy-b-ionone Phytol trans-Geranylgeraniol
			Sterols and triterpenoids	b-Sitosterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate Campesterol Brassicasterol Cycloartenyl acetate b-Amyrin Squalene
			Other compounds	g-Tocopherol Vitamin E d-Docecalactone Cyclodecanol Cyclohexadecane Cyclohexane, tetradecyl- Cyclohexene derivatives Cyclopentane, 1-ethyl-1-methyl-
48.	<i>Plagiothecium undulatum</i>	X25_SW_MC_279 X25_SW_Et_279	Nucleotides and primary metabolites	Sucrose
			Flavonoids and other phenolic compounds	Apigenin
			Fatty acids and their esters	9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid
			Terpenoids (mono-, sesqui-, and diterpenoids)	(E)-5-[(1S,8aS)-5,5,8a-trimethyl-2-methylidene-3,4,4a,6,7,8-hexahydro-1H-naphthalen-1-yl]-3-(hydroxymethyl)-2-oxopent-3-enoic acid